

ANALYSIS OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE PATTERNS OF MULTINATIONAL CORPORATIONS

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Abstract: *The aim of this paper is to find out whether multinational corporations have the same capital structure. Capital structure refers to the way a firm finances its assets and corresponds to the ratio of its own and borrowed long term resources. Financial decisions are key decisions in corporate finance since they directly influence company's sustainability and growth. In general, the decision on financing is not about the choice between debt and equity, but is rather about selecting the most adequate proportion of the two. The decision about equity and debt mix capital structure is influenced by taking into account income, risk, suitability, control and timing. These factors vary to a great extent from a company to a company, from industry to industry, depending on the characteristics mentioned in this paper and the particular situation of the company. This paper is significant for Multinational corporations, education institutions, financial industry, and organization management.*

Keywords: *corporate finance, capital structure, optimization, cost of capital, wacc of capital, exchange rate and political risk*

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this paper is to find out whether multinational corporations have the same capital structure. In order to consider this question we have surveyed various articles, papers and books dealing with international corporate funding. The reference list is given at the end of this paper.

Multinational corporations are defined as firms that have operations in more than one country, international sales and nationality mix among owners and managers. (1)

Capital structure refers to the way a firm finances its assets and corresponds to the ratio of its own and borrowed long term resources. Financial decisions are key decisions in corporate finance since they directly influence company's sustainability and growth. Taking into account that a common goal of a company is to maximize its value and shareholders' wealth, financial decisions mostly refers to the capital structure decisions. (2) Capital structure significantly differs due to a specific form of a company and industry, and consists of a combination of equity (retained earnings and funds obtained by issuing shares), debt (borrowed funds) or hybrid securities. Apart from a company's form, a capital structure depends on the various factors that should be taken into account when composing the company's capital structure. The most important factors are: rule of funding, business risk, retain control over the company, preserving the ability of funding, company's life cycle phase, and industry life cycle phase. (3) Multinational corporations finance their operations by using a capital structure that can minimize their cost of capital in order to achieve maximum value of those operations. (4)

Some of the most extensive research in corporate finance is the capital structure choice. Capital structure studies aim to explain the mix of securities and financing sources used by multinational corporations to finance a real investment and its operations. Most of the research on capital structure has focused on the proportions of equity versus debt reported the corporations' balance sheets, as well as on factors that influence decisions on capital structure.

According to the Modigliani and Miller (1958), the value of a firm is invariant, constant to its capital structure in an efficient market world, without taxes or a bankruptcy cost. This irrelevance theory has been modified and improved in terms of understanding capital structure when taking into account the deviations from perfect markets such as bankruptcy costs, taxes, and costs related to agency problems. Modern theories of capital structure consider real world costs and frictions. Also, they include theories such as the trade-off theory, agency cost theory (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Jensen, 1986; Myers, 1977), pecking order theory (Myers and Majluf, 1984), and asymmetric information theory (Ross, 1977). Empirical studies such as Titman and Wessels (1988), Harris and Raviv (1991), and Frank and Goyal (2004) confirm the importance of these firm-level determinants of capital structure. The general agreement is that a firm's level of leverage is related to its size, investment opportunities, profitability, fixed assets, tax rates, bankruptcy probability, dividend policy, and the industry average leverage (Myers, 2001). (5)

For multinational corporations that have operations in foreign markets, the cost of capital may differ from domestic firms due to the following characteristics that make MNCs different from domestic companies (DC): firm's size, access to international capital markets, international diversification, exposure to the exchange rate change, exposure to country risk. (6) Some empirical research such as Michel and Shaked (1986) research indicate that MNCs are less leveraged than domestic companies. Fatemi (1988) also finds that MNCs have lower debt ratios than domestic companies. Furthermore, his results show that multinational corporations use more short-term debt financing than domestic companies do. 'In a benchmark study, Lee and Kwok (1988) suggest an analytical framework that examines the impact of international environmental factors (e.g. political risk, foreign exchange risk) on the firm-related capital structure determinants (e.g. agency costs, bankruptcy costs) that in turn influence the capital structure of MNCs. Using the foreign tax ratio to classify companies as either MNCs or DCs, Lee and Kwok then compare the agency costs of debt, the bankruptcy costs and the long-term debt ratios of MNCs and DCs. Their results suggest that even after adjusting for industry and size effects, MNCs have higher agency costs than DCs. In contrast, they report that after controlling of the size effect, there is no difference in the bankruptcy costs of MNCs and DCs. Lee and Kwok also find that MNCs are less leveraged than DCs even when they control of the size effect. Burgman (1996) extends Lee and Kwok's work by directly estimating the effect of foreign exchange risk and political risk on the capital structure of MNCs. Using the foreign tax ratio to classify firms as either MNCs or DCs and control of industry and size effects, Burgman finds that MNCs have lower debt ratios and higher agency costs than DCs. Furthermore, international diversification does not appear to lower earnings volatility. To estimate the sensitivity of a firm to foreign exchange risk, Burgman conducts a regression analysis of the stock returns of each sample firm on the returns of an index of U.S. stocks and on the U.S.\$:SDR returns. His political risk measure is based on the following ratio: number of low political risk countries to the total number of countries in which the firm operates. Low political risk countries are the top 20 in the country risk rankings provided by *Euromoney* in 1989. The results of the regression analysis for his sample of MNCs suggest that the debt ratios of these companies are positively related to both risks. Burgman concludes that this evidence is consistent with the hypothesis that MNCs use debt policy as a tool to hedge foreign exchange risk and a political risk. Moreover, Chen et al. (1997) conducted a regression analysis to investigate the effect of international activities (as measured by foreign pre-tax income) on capital structure. In accordance with previous findings, the authors report that even after controlling for the firm size, agency costs of debt, bankruptcy costs and profitability, the long-term debt ratios of MNCs are lower than those of DCs. However, within their sample of MNCs, debt ratios increase with the level of international activities. As pointed out by the authors, this result is interesting and calls for further investigation.' (7)

Jung et al. (1996) have found that companies should use equity to finance their growth with explanation that such financing reduces agency's costs between shareholders and managers, and companies with less growth prospects should use debt because it has a disciplinary role (Jensen, 1986; Stulz, 1990). Myers (1977) has found that firms with growth opportunities may invest sub-

optimally, and therefore creditors will be more reluctant to lend for long horizons. This problem could be resolved by short-term financing (Titman and Wessels, 1988) or by convertible bonds (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Smith and Warner, 1979). Hovakimian et al. (2001) argued that large stock price increases are usually associated with improved growth opportunities, which leads to a lower debt ratio. (8)

Multinational corporations tend to be more diversified, and accordingly their cash flows are less volatile. Titman and Wessels (1988, p. 6), argued that 'relatively large firms tend to be (. . .) less prone to bankruptcy'. Ferri and Jones (1979) have suggested that large firms have easier access to the markets and can borrow at better conditions. (9)

With reference to a relationship between leverage and company's profitability, there are different opinions. According to the *pecking order theory*, companies prefer to use internal sources of financing firstly, then debt, and finally external equity obtained by stock issues. All things being equal, the more profitable the firms are, the more internal financing they will have, and therefore a negative relationship between leverage and profitability is expected. An opposite opinion is in *trade-off theory* view, which says that when companies are profitable, they should prefer debt to benefit from tax shield. (10)

'Firms attempt to use a specific capital structure, or mix of capital components, that will minimize their cost of capital. The lower a firm's cost of capital; the lower is its required rate of return on a given proposed project. Firms estimate their cost of capital before they conduct capital budgeting because the Net Present Value of any project is partially dependent on the cost of capital.' (11) MNCs should choose a capital structure that minimizes consolidated cost of capital.

According to the literature, a key driver of company's capital structure choice is the desire to attain and preserve financial flexibility (Myers and Majluf, 1984; Pinegar and Wilbricht, 1989; Graham and Harvey, 2001; Bancel and Mittoo, 2004; Brounen et al., 2004). (12)

Based on the literature researched, there is no one universal and unique theory regarding capital structure and debt – equity choice of multinational corporations. On the whole, all cited theories are useful to better understand capital structure and what should be taken into account in decision making process along with the all relevant factors influencing the capital structure choice. For example, the *trade-off theory* shows that companies seek debt levels that balance the tax advantages of additional debt against the costs of possible financial distress. This theory predicts moderate borrowing by tax-paying firms; while the *pecking order* theory argues that the company will borrow, rather than issuing equity, when the internal cash flow is not sufficient to fund capital expenditures. Hence, the amount of debt will reflect the company's cumulative need for external funds. The *free cash flow* theory concerns that dangerously high debt levels will increase value, despite the threat of financial distress, when a company's operating cash flow significantly exceed its profitable investment opportunities. This theory mostly refers to mature companies that are prone to over invest. On the another hand, there is a theory of Modigliani and Miller (1958) which says that perhaps financing does not matter and argue that the choice between equity and debt financing has no effect on the company's value or on the cost or availability of capital. They assumed perfect and frictionless capital markets, in which financial innovation would quickly extinguish any deviation from their predicted equilibrium. (13)

This paper consists of section II in which capital sources, pattern of capital structure, international factors and their expected effect on a capital structure of multinational corporation, cost of capital, costs of debt and equity composition, Modigliani-Miller propositions of capital structure, debt and taxes, taxes and the trade-off theory and the pecking order theory have been analyzed, and in final section the conclusion. At the end, in section IV, list of used literature is given.

2. MAIN BODY

Multinational corporations (MNCs) operate across national boundaries in many different countries with widely varying economic, political, financial, market, tax and legal structures, currency risks and business conditions. A decision regarding a capital structure of multinational corporations has to reflect local conditions and a parent company's needs related to consolidated structure of capital and the final goal to maximize the overall company value. This complexity gives rise to a number of questions and one of them is how to choose the best or optimal capital structure for an MNC. (14) 'The optimal capital structure is the one that strikes a balance between risk and return and thereby maximizes the price of the stock and simultaneously minimizes the cost of capital'. (15)

2.1. Capital sources

General view on capital sources may be divided into two main sources of financing: internal and external. Internal sources relate to the sources within a company, while external sources refer to outside sources of funds. Yet, capital may be financed in long or short terms horizons.

Internal sources of financing may consist of depreciation provisions, reserve funds or retained earnings, while external sources may consist of share capital, bond capital, loans and advances. Share capital represents ownership or equity capital of the company, whereas bonds and loans are considered as borrowed or debt capital. Capital that consist of issue of shares, debentures or bonds represent the primary capital sourcing. (16)

2.2. Patterns of capital structure

There are several forms of capital structure:

- Absolute equity share capital
- Different proportion of equity and debt capital
- Different proportion of equity and preference shares capital
- Different proportion of equity, preference and debt capital

a) Advantages and disadvantages of equity share capital

Multinational corporations have various advantages of issuing equity shares. Some of them are: it is a long run and permanent source of capital, by issuing of equity share capital - there is no changes on the assets of a company, a company can trade on equity in unfavorable period on the risk of equity capital, dividend policy, collecting more income by trading on equity, right to participate in the voting, control process and management access, capital profits.

Multinational corporations have certain disadvantages in terms of equity shares. Some of them are: rarefaction of control, equity shares are transferable and saleable which leads to diluting the voting power, excessive issue of equity shares may result in over-capitalization; no flexibility in capital structure, it may costs the companies more than financing with other sources of capital, equity shares of good companies are subject to hectic speculation in the stock market. Their prices may be frequently fluctuated which is not in the company's interest. (17)

b) Advantages and disadvantages of using debt capital structure

Companies' first choice for composing capital structure is often a debt capital structure which contributes to total lower financing costs. Generally, a debt capital structure contributes to keeping profit in terms of increase returns on equity and secure tax savings to company. In comparison

with equity, debt requires lower financing cost. Therefore, companies tend to mix debt in the capital structure in order to subdue the average cost of funds. A long term debt represents the obligation by a company that is contractually related and that should be returned (principal and interest) at the specified period, till maturity. In the case of company liquidation, debt holders have the claiming right to company assets, which gives them certainty of protection for investments. To summarize, a safer debt investment requires less cost compensation. Moreover, by using debt as a source of financing, companies are obliged to pay interests regardless of their profits, while equity is in close correlation to profit: the more profits a company makes, the more it has to share with equity investors. Companies often use debt to finance stable business operations in which the interest and principal can be easily repaid and to keep the rest of yield profit for them. Yet, advantages of using a debt in financing the business operations lays in effects of financial leverages and tax savings.

Disadvantages of using a debt capital structure are reflected in some potential problems such as ongoing financial liabilities and potential bankruptcy risk. The more debt financing – the higher risk of bankruptcy companies may face. (18)

c) Advantages and disadvantages of preference shares capital

Preference shares are a hybrid source of capital and are mostly used by big corporations as long term source of financing their business operations. Preference shares, as hybrid source of capital financing, share attributes of both equity and debt.

From companies' point of view advantages of preference shares lay in the fact that there is no form of legal obligation for dividend payment, improvement in borrowing capacity, no dilution in control and no charge on assets.

However, there are some disadvantages of using preference shares as a source of financing. Preference shares are very costly source of finance, which is the major disadvantage of this kind of financing. Yet, preference shares have preferential rights everywhere. (19)

2.3. International factors and their expected effect on a capital structure of Multinational Corporation

There are several international factors that influence a capital structure of a multinational corporation. These factors are: business risk and diversification, exchange rate and political risk, agency costs, country risk.

a) Business risk and diversification

Business risk such as expected bankruptcy cost, cost of financial distress 'is often proxy by the volatility of net operating income, and most (but not all) of the previous empirical studies have found the expected negative relationship between volatility and leverage. It is also frequently argued that, due to their ability to diversify across less than perfectly correlated national economies, volatility should be less for MNCs than for DCs, and that MNCs should therefore be able to support more leverage. However, Lee [1986] and Fatemi [1988] have found that MNCs actually have lower leverage ratios than DCs.' (20)

b) Exchange rate and political risk

Multinational corporations and domestic companies are exposed to an exchange rate risk which may influence the demand, supply, cost and price of a company. 'Since FASB 52 mandated the use of the current rate method in 1981, translation gains/losses no longer pass through to the income statement. Furthermore, U.S. accounting standards allow some flexibility to smooth reported

earnings. Hence, an economic exchange rate exposure measure based on reported earnings is seriously limited, and a measure based on stock prices or analysts' expectations would be more appropriate.' (21) A traditional approach argue that the more corporation is exposed to exchange rate fluctuations, the greater expected bankruptcy costs are and therefore, lower optimal level of debt is. Yet, 'MNCs with higher economic exchange rate exposure should have higher debt levels. However, the distinction between trans-action and economic exchange rate exposure is important here. It is relatively easy for a firm to hedge its transaction exposure to exchange rate fluctuations. On the other hand, it is difficult to measure economic exchange rate risk and even more difficult to hedge it.' (22)

Besides exchange rate risk, MNCs are also exposed to political risks which are difficult to adequately diversify. Debt policy is one of the tools that MNCs use in order to response to this kind of risk. 'Corporations can minimize the expected loss due to a major political event in a risky foreign country by financing mostly with a local debt, or by borrowing from a syndicate of international banks. Hence, it can be argued that MNCs that operate in riskier countries should be expected to have higher debt ratios.' (23)

c) Agency costs

Agency costs significantly affect the optimal debt level of a company. There are a number of differences between MNCs and DCs in these costs which include: monitoring costs, international labor market imperfections and different asset structures. 'MNCs face higher auditing costs, language differences, sovereignty uncertainties, and varying legal and accounting systems. In addition, their investors are confronted with wider informational gaps and higher costs of investigation. Thus, MNCs are likely to face significantly higher monitoring costs than DCs. The existence of capital and labor market imperfections could also lead to higher agency costs for MNCs.' (24)

d) Country risk

Multinational corporations may face the possibility that a host country's government revokes assets of subsidiary. This possibility is influenced by many factors. 'If assets are seized and fair compensation is not provided, the probability of the MNC's going bankrupt increases. The higher the percentage of an MNC's assets invested in foreign countries and the higher the overall country risk of operating in these countries, the higher will be the MNC's probability of bankruptcy (and therefore its cost of capital), other things being equal.' (25) Changes in host tax laws of a government may also affect a cash flow of MNC subsidiary. (26)

2.4. Cost of capital

a) Comparing the cost of equity and debt

The cost of capital refers to the cost of company's both ways of financing, debt and equity, and represents the required rate or return on invested funds. A model for a company's weighed average cost of capital that can be applied in calculations is as follows and reflects the percentage of debt and equity as capital components:

$$k_c = \left(\frac{D}{D + E} \right) k_d (1 - t) + \left(\frac{E}{D + E} \right) k_e$$

Where:

- '**k_c** - Weighted average cost of capital
- D** - Amount of the firm's debt
- k_d** - Before-tax cost of its debt

- t** - Corporate tax rate
- E** - Firm's equity
- ke** - Cost of financing with equity' (27)

b) Cost of capital for multinational corporations (28)

Measuring the cost of capital sources is a complex subject and as it is stated in the paper, it is desirable for multinational corporations to minimize the overall cost of capital. This should result in making decision on an optimal capital structure that leads to the minimum cost of funds. In order for an investment to be meaningful, the expected return on capital should be greater than the cost of capital.

Cost of debt consists of the rate of interest paid and could be calculated 'by taking the rate on a risk free bond whose duration matches the term structure of the corporate debt, then adding a default premium':

(R_f + credit risk rate)(1-T)

R_f - Represents the risk free rate

T - The corporate tax rate

Cost of equity, broadly defined, represents the risk-weighted projected return required by investors and is equal to: Risk free rate of return + Premium expected for risk

Cost of equity = Risk free rate of return + Beta x (market rate of return- risk free rate of return) where Beta= sensitivity to movements in the relevant market

$$E_s = R_f + \beta_s(R_m - R_f).$$

Where:

E_s - The expected return for a security

R_f - The expected risk-free return in that market (government bond yield)

β_s - The sensitivity to market risk for the security

R_M - The historical return of the stock market/ equity market

(R_M-R_f) - The risk premium of market assets over risk free assets.

To estimate the required return, besides the CAPM model as above, the Fama–French three-factor model may be applied.

Expected return or required rate of return for investors could be calculated with the 'dividend capitalization mode' as presented by a formula:

$$K_{cs} = \frac{Dividend_{Payment/Share}}{Price_{Market}} + Growth_{rate}.$$

2.5. Costs of debt and equity composition

The costs of equity and debt may be composed to bring out an overall cost of capital of a multinational corporation. The costs of debt and equity differ from country to country and it is comprehensible that the cost of capital could be lower for the companies based in specific countries such Japan. Japan commonly has a relatively low cost of capital. (29)

The following illustration aims to better understanding of the concept of overall capital cost.

The costs of debt (after tax) and of equity capital at various levels of debt equity mix are estimated as follows:

Table 1: Cost of debt and equity capital

<i>Debt as percentage of total capital employed</i>	<i>Cost of debt (%)</i>	<i>Cost of equity (%)</i>
0	10	15
20	10	15
40	12	16
50	13	18
60	14	20

What will be the optimal cost of capital? In order to determine the optimal debt equity mix, it is necessary to compute the cost of capital.

Table 2: The computed cost of capital

K_i %	K_e %	p_1	p_2	$K_i p_1 + K_e p_2 = K_o$
10	15	0.0	1.00	$0 + 15.0 = 15$
10	15	0.2	0.8	$2.0 + 12.0 = 14$
12	16	0.4	0.6	$4.8 + 9.6 = 14.4$
13	18	0.6	0.5	$7.8 + 9.0 = 16.8$
14	20	0.6	0.4	$8.4 + 8.0 = 16.4$

In the table above, **Ko** is equal to **Kip1+Kep2**

Where:

Ki = Cost of debt

pl = Relative proportion of debt in the total capital of the firm

Ke = Cost of equity

p2 = Relative proportion of equity in the total capital of the firm

The optimal capital structure is the one where the cost of capital is at minimum. From the given example, it is evident that 20% of debt and 80% of equity gives the minimum composed cost of capital (result $K_o = 14\%$). Any other option of equity and debt would make higher the overall cost of capital to the company. (30) This example shows that it seems that the best capital structure composition is the combination of equity and debt. In addition to the given example, it seems that multinational companies do not necessarily have the same capital structure.

Most of piled gross investments by U.S. nonfinancial corporations have been financed from internal cash flow: depreciation and retained earnings, while external financing in most years constitute less than 20% of real investment and most of that financing is debt. 'Net stock issues are frequently negative: that is, more shares are extinguished in acquisitions and share repurchase programs than are created by new stock issues. For example, in 1999 internal cash flow financed about 85 percent of aggregate investment by U.S. nonfarm, nonfinancial corporations (\$805 billion out of \$944 billion). External financing was \$139 billion. Corporations raised this sum by net additional borrowing of \$283 billion; net share issues were negative at \$144 billion (Federal Reserve System, 1999, Flow of Funds Accounts, Table F.102). Of course, these are aggregated figures.' (31)

There are companies that rely heavily on stock issues. These companies tend to be smaller, riskier and more rapid in growth.

A debt ratio is different across various industries. For example, 'the large, integrated oil companies have relied mostly on debt for external financing. Many of these companies have simultaneously retired equity through share repurchases. Exxon spent \$29 billion on share repurchases from the mid-1980s to its merger with Mobil in 1999. Other relatively heavy debt users include the utility, chemical, transportation, telecommunications, forest products and real estate development industries. At the other extreme, the major pharmaceutical companies typically operate at negative debt ratios: their holdings of cash and marketable securities exceed their outstanding debt, so they are net lenders. Other net lenders include Ford Motor Co., which had roughly \$25 billion of cash and marketable securities in 2000 vs. \$10 billion of outstanding debt. Debt ratios are also low or negative for many prominent growth companies. At mid-year 2000, Microsoft had no long-term debt but held \$24 billion in cash and marketable securities.' (32)

'Marketing and advertising intensive companies such as Procter & Gamble have traditionally operated at low debt ratios. Their profits flow mainly from intangible assets. Firms with valuable growth opportunities also tend to have low debt ratios (Long and Malitz, 1985; Smith and Watts, 1992; Barclay, Smith and Watts, 1995; Barclay and Smith, 1999).' (33)

In addition to the previous examples, it may be argued that when profitability and business risks are high, industry debt ratios are low or negative. Also, this may indicate that multinational corporations do not have the same capital structure.

2.6. Modigliani-Miller Propositions of capital structure

Modigliani and Miller (1958), theory considers the value of a firm as invariant, constant to its capital structure in an efficient markets world without taxes or a bankruptcy cost.

The figure below shows a simple, market value balance sheet:

Assets-in-place and growth opportunities	Debt (D)
	Equity (E)
	Firm value (V)

Figure 1: A Market-value Balance Sheet

A total company's value (V) consists of company's debt (D) and equity (E). According to the Modigliani and Miller's (1958) proposition, a value of the company is constant, regardless of the debt and equity proportions. Leverage irrelevance generalizes to any mix of securities issued by the company: it is not important whether the debt is long term or short term, callable or call protected, straight or convertible, in home or foreign currency. Moreover, this proposition says that each cost of capital is constant, regardless of the debt ratio.

$$\text{Weighted average cost of capital} = r_A = r_D D/V + r_E E/V$$

Where:

' r_D and r_E be the cost of debt and the cost of equity, i.e. the expected rates of return demanded by investors in the firm's debt and equity securities. The overall (weighted-average) cost of capital depends on these costs and the market-value ratios of debt and equity to overall firm value.' (34)

'The weighted average cost of capital r_A is the expected return on a portfolio of all the firm's outstanding securities. It is also the discount or 'hurdle rate' for capital investment. The weighted

average cost of capital r_A is, according to Modigliani and Miller, a constant. Also, debt has a prior claim on the firm's assets and earnings, so the cost of debt is always less than the cost of equity. Suppose we solve the equation for the cost of equity.' (35)

$$r_E = r_A + (r_A - r_D)D/E$$

In other words, the cost of equity - the expected rate of return demanded by equity investors increases with the market value debt - equity ratio: D/E . (36)

According to this proposition of Modigliani and Miller's, any attempt to switch 'cheap' debt for 'expensive' equity fails to reduce the overall capital cost. (37)

The question is whether the capital markets are really perfect enough to put this theory into practice for all multinational corporations' capital structure?

2.7. Debt and taxes

'The United States taxes yield corporate income, but interest is a tax-deductible expense. A taxpaying firm that pays an extra dollar of interest receives a partially offsetting "interest tax shield" in the form of lower taxes paid.' (38) Financing by debt instead of equity increases the total after tax dollar return and accordingly, may increase the value of company. As Modigliani and Miller (1963) presumed, debt is fixed and permanent. Corporate income is taxed at the current 35% statutory rate. 'The firm borrows \$1 million and repurchases and retires \$1 million of equity. It commits to maintain this debt level and to make annual interest payments for the indefinite future. In the case when there are no taxes, this new debt does not increase or decrease a firm value: the firm is borrowing on fair terms, so the money raised is exactly offset by the present value of the future interest payments. But for a taxpaying firm the net liability created by the \$1 million debt issue is only \$650,000, because the Internal Revenue Service effectively pays 35 percent of the interest payments. The after-tax net present value of this transaction would be $NPV = +1 - .65 = +\$0.35$ million. The gains from borrowing \$10 million or \$500 million scale up proportionally. Such calculations are now understood as remote upper bounds.' (39)

Debt is not fixed, permanent and constant. Debt depends on the future value of the company and profitability, accordingly. If a company does well -> it will be able to increase borrowing and opposite, if company does poorly -> it will be forced to pay down debt. Next, the company may not be always profitable and therefore, the average effective future tax rate is less than the statutory rate. 'Third, the corporate-level tax advantages of debt could be partly offset by the tax advantage of equity to individual investors, namely, the ability to defer capital gains and then to pay taxes at a lower capital gains rate. The tax rate on investors' interest and dividend income is higher than the effective tax rate on equity income, which comes as a mixture of dividends and capital gains.' (40)

2.8. Taxes and the trade-off theory

The trade-off theory says that 'company will borrow up to the point where the marginal value of tax shields on additional debt is just offset by the increase in the present value of possible costs of financial distress.' (41) There are many companies that are profitable with good credit ratings operating for years with low debt ratios, such as Microsoft and the major pharmaceutical companies. Studies of the actual debt ratios persistently argue that the most profitable companies in a selected industry tend to borrow least. 'For example: Wald (1999) found that profitability was the single largest determinant of debt/ asset ratios in cross-sectional tests for the United States, United Kingdom, Germany, France and Japan.' (42) High profit organizations that have more taxable income to shield in order to be able to service more debt without risking financial distress, have low debt ratios.

The trade-off theory of optimal capital structure rationalizes moderate debt ratios which is consistent with certain facts such as that companies with relatively safe business tend to borrow more than more risky companies.

2.9. The pecking order theory

Myers and Majluf analyzed companies with assets in place and a growth opportunity requiring additional financing with the assumption that financial markets are perfect, except that investors do not know the real value of existing assets or the new opportunity. Accordingly, investors are not able to value precisely the issued securities to finance new investments.

The Pecking Order theory provides the answer why the main external financing comes from debt. Yet, it explains that more profitable companies are, they have more internal financing available and therefore borrow less, while less profitable companies require external financing and consequently accrue debt.

Previous theories are conditional theories of capital structure. Each highlights certain costs and benefits of alternative financing strategies. 'Treynor (1981), Donaldson (1983) and Myers (1993, 2000b) suggest that the firm acts to maximize the present value of current and future benefits to 'insiders'. The benefits come in various forms: cash, over and above opportunity wages; stock or options in the firm; and private benefits, such as perquisites.' (43) However, multinational corporations have to be very careful when making capital structure decisions and should consider all possible forms and factors that may influence them.

3. CONCLUSION

A multinational corporation's capital structure decision is influenced by corporate characteristics including: liquidity, stability of cash flows, and access to earnings, credit risk and overall profitability. Moreover, a capital structure is also influenced by features of the countries where a multinational corporation operates such as interest rates, strength of local currencies, stock restrictions, tax laws and country risk. Taking into account that some of the mentioned characteristics support the usage of equity intensive capital structure, while other support a debt intensive structure, definitely there is no a single general rule, and a capital structure of multinational corporations may depend on the specific mix of countries in which a company does business. (44) A capital structure is composed of various sources of long term finance in the total capital of a multinational corporation. A capital structure consists of the two main sources: ownership and creditorship securities (equity and debt). Both types are used by most of large industrial companies. Which type and / or proportion a multinational corporation will choose depends on many factors analyzed in this paper, taking into account all possible forms of financing before making a final decision, having in mind the ultimate goal: maximization of the MNCs value.

A capital structure planning is of high importance to any company, multinational and domestic since it has a considerable bearing on its profitability. A wrong capital structure decision may be very costly for the company. When a multinational corporation makes a decision about a capital structure, due attention should be paid to objectives such as liquidity, solvency, flexibility and profitability. Liquidity is very important, even more important than profitability. The final decision of the amount of debt and other fixed return securities and variable income securities, namely equity shares, is to be made after taking into consideration all internal and external factors related to the multinational corporation's operations and after analyzing and comparing each kind of features of securities.

In general, the decision on financing is not about the choice between debt and equity, but is rather about selecting the most adequate proportion of the two. The decision about equity and debt mix capital structure is influenced by taking into account income, risk, suitability, control and timing. These factors vary to a great extent from a company to a company, from industry to industry, depending on the characteristics mentioned in this paper and the particular situation of the company.

Based on arguments given here, it seems that there is no an exact mathematical model for a decision on a capital structure; therefore, an appropriate managers' judgment plays an important role in analyzing all the factors, forms of financing and conflicting forces before a final decision on capital structure is reached taking into account the main goal of a company.

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